

Effects of 7Es Model and Problem-Based Strategy on Performance in Wave Motion among Secondary School Students in Bauchi Metropolis

Omega, Joy Okache¹
 joyokache@yahoo.com.uk
 08033674749

Kpiranyam, Felix Sesugh¹
 sughkpiranyam@gmail.com
 08070697096

¹Department of Science and Mathematics Education, Benue State University, Makurdi

Abstract

This study examined the effects of 7Es model and problem-based strategy on performance in wave motion among secondary school students in Bauchi Metropolis. Three research questions were answered while three corresponding null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study employed pre-test post-test, non-randomized quasi-experimental research design involving two treatment groups. Population for study comprised 3579 (71 Male and 57 Female) Senior Secondary class Two (SS II) students offering Physics during the 2022/2023 Academic session among government secondary schools in Bauchi Metropolis. Sample comprised 128 SS II physics students consisting of 71 males and 57 females obtained using simple random sampling technique by balloting technique. Wave Motion Performance Test (WMPT) with reliability coefficient of 0.80 obtained using Kuder-Richardson Formula 21 (K-R 21) was used to collect data. Trained research assistants taught in the sampled schools use lesson plans prepared following tenets of 7Es model and Problem-Based Learning (PBL) strategy. Research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation while Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the formulated null hypotheses. Findings revealed: no statistical significant difference in performance of students taught wave motion using 7Es learning model and those taught using PBL strategy [$F(1,125)=1.756, P=0.188>0.05$]. It was concluded that the use of 7Es learning model and PBL strategy enhanced students' academic performance in wave motion. It was recommended among others that, Physics teachers should use 7Es model but PBL should be used with care in attempt to improve male and female students' performance in wave motion.

Keyword: 7Es Learning Model, PBL Strategy, Performance, Wave Motion

Introduction

Physics plays an important role in all the natural sciences, Achor (2020) views Physics as a branch of natural science which deals with matter, its motion and behaviour through space and time and the related entities of energy and force. The ultimate aim of Physics is to explain unified set of laws governing matter, motion, and energy at small (microscopic) subatomic distances and human (macroscopic) scale of everyday life. It could also extend to the largest distances like those on the extragalactic scale (Haruna, 2019). Physics knowledge and skills are applied in other branches of sciences such as Biology and Chemistry. However, Physics is reputed to contain concepts that are more abstract compared to other sciences (Achor, 2020) of which one of such concepts is wave motion.

Several researches on the issue of academic performance of secondary school students offering Physics show that there is decline in academic performance of students in Physics (Adeyemo, Babajide & Iwuji, 2014; Omebe & Akani, 2015; Josiah & Mankilik, 2021; Offordile, Umeano, Adene, Obi, Ugwuanyi, Okeke, & Adimora, 2021). Evidence from West Africa Examination Council (WAEC) chief examiners report also attest to the fact that performance of students in Physics has dwindled over the years (WAEC, 2015-2021).

Year	Total Number of Registered candidates	Mean Scores	Standard Deviation
2015	658,393	19.00	9.90
2016	666,992	19.00	8.83
2017	704,504	15.00	8.43
2018	728,924	26.00	9.80

Effects of 7Es Model ... (Omega & Kpianyam, 2024) DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11432175>

2019	762,340	26.00	9.95
2020	749,752	34.00	9.33
2021	759,232	22.00	8.37

Source: WAEC Chief Examiners Report (2015-2021).

The teaching and learning of Physics particularly wave motion is faced with some challenges leading to students' poor performance in Physics. The major challenges according to Assem, Nartey, Appiah and Aidoo (2023), are poor quality of Physics teachers and teaching methods employed by these teachers to teach Physics. Especially in abstract Physics concepts like mechanics, electromagnetism, gravitation and wave motion. The use of defective methods of teaching limit students' active involvement in learning of Physics. Hence, this poses serious danger not only as obstacles to students' academic performance but as hindrance in the nations efforts to produce Physics specialists for national scientific and economic development. Students' poor academic performance in Physics at the senior secondary school level means that the number of students opting to study Physics and Physics related courses in higher institutions will decline resulting in low manpower, infrastructural and economic development. As Bunkure (2019) observed, Physics is a pre-requisite for courses like Medicine, Geology, Agricultural Science and Pharmacy. Other are Engineering, Architecture, Astronomy and Physics Education.

The issue of poor performance in Physics is a source of concern as the underperformance of students in Physics has attracted attention of government, researchers, and professional organisations like the Science Teachers Association of Nigeria (STAN), curriculum planners, Physics teachers, parents and students. Attempts have been made by different stakeholders to emphasize that teaching of science be more student-oriented. Professional organisations like STAN has consistently organize workshops to upgrade teachers on current trends in teaching and learning of science.

Over the years, researchers globally have also conducted studies aimed at improving academic performance of students in Physics. These studies focus on innovative teaching strategies that could enhance students' performance in Physics concepts particularly wave motion. Some of these innovative teaching strategies include the 5Es and 7Es learning model (Onyilo, Tine, Kpiranyam & Wirba, 2022). Others include Problem-Based Learning Strategy, Think-Pair-Share Strategy, Student Team Achievement Division Strategy and Project-Based Learning Strategy among others (Omega, 2017; Kpiranyam, Agbidye & Ukor, 2022; Strobel Education, 2023). For the purpose of this study, the researchers considered the use of 7Es learning model and Problem-Based learning strategy to enhance students' performance in wave motion.

Wave motion is one of the topics taught in Senior Secondary Two (SS II) Physics curriculum. It is a topic considered by students to be difficult because it involves the use of formulas and drawings with lots of related concepts in it such as reflection, refraction, diffraction, interference. Students sometimes have difficulties differentiating between these concepts which could be some of the reasons responsible for poor academic performance. Students' poor performance in wave motion could also be traceable to many other factors among which are the teaching methodologies employed by the teachers (Josiah & Mankilik, 2021). There is therefore the need to use a learner centered approach in the teaching and learning of physics. It is against this backdrop that the researchers sort to see if the use of innovative teaching strategies such as 7Es learning model and Problem-Based learning strategy could enhance students' performance in wave motion.

The 5Es learning model was developed initially by Robert Bybee based on the works of German Philosopher Freidrich Herbert (Bybee, 1997) and was modified by Sadeq (2003) to generate 7Es learning model. The 7Es learning model has seven stages which include Elicit, Engage, Explore, Explain, Elaborate, Evaluate and Extend. It aims at enabling students to build their scientific knowledge acquisition by themselves. The 7Es learning model enable learners acquire concepts and apply them in new contexts and real situations thereby developing students' skills of applying scientific method, problem solving ability, engaging in dialogue and team work which may improve their performance in Physics. In addition, it could help students view abstract concepts differently (Khataibeh, 2005; Adesoji & Idika, 2015; Cakir, 2017; Abuh, 2021). Thus, 7Es learning model has the potential and could improve students' academic performance as it enables them construct active knowledge through mind-on and hands-on activities. Cheronon, Samikwo and Kabesa (2021) posits that this strategy gives learners opportunity to collaborate with peers through interactions, thus learners are able to learn effectively and develop critical thinking skills. The strategy can enhance students' performance in Physics in Benue State (Onyilo, Agernor, Kpiranyam & Wirba, 2022).

Another learning strategy that could help foster students' performance in wave motion is the Problem-Based learning strategy. Problem-Based Learning Strategy (PBL) is a student centred pedagogy. With this strategy, students learn about physics concepts such as wave motion through the experience of problem solving. PBL strategy is the process of acquiring new knowledge based on the recognition of a need to learn. The role of the teacher in a PBL classroom is to facilitate learning by supporting, guiding and monitoring the learning process. The PBL strategy is activity based, promotes interaction among

Effects of 7Es Model ... (Omaga & Kpianyam, 2024) DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11432175>

learners, encourages active learning and the acquisition of problem solving proficiency among learners. According to Hun School of Princeton (2020), some of the benefits of PBL strategy include promotion of self-learning, high engagement in learning and developing transferable skills. Others are; it improves team work among learners and encourages intrinsic rewards. Researches indicate that PBL strategy can enhance students' performance (Ajai & Imoko, 2015; Omaga, 2017).

Physics classrooms in Nigeria contain male and female students distinguished as such based on biological characteristics. Gender issue permeate science classrooms, Physics inclusive. As regards the use of 7Es learning model, Al-Eid (2014), Balta and Sarac (2016) in their separate studies found no significant difference in the academic performance of students exposed to 7Es learning model based on gender of students. Corroborating the assertion, Nnamani and Oyibe (2016) aptly stated that intrinsically, there is practically no significant difference in the intelligence quotient of males and females that can be traceable to gender difference. Shalini and Anurag, (2018) also reported that 7Es learning model is gender friendly. Similarly, Ibrahim, Lakpini, Abdulkarim and Falau (2022) stated that 7Es learning model can improve students' performance irrespective of their gender. Studies by Mergendollar, Maxwell and Bellisimo (2002), Anyafulude (2014), Ajai and Imoko (2015), Omaga (2017) in other locations showed that PBL does not discriminate in terms of enhancing male and female students' performance. By implication, with PBL strategy, as male and female students collaborate and solve problems, they gain during the learning process which could improve their performance. However, in most secondary schools across the study area of this research, the use of defective methods has resulted in low performance of students in Physics (Usman & Yakubu, 2020; Ogonna & Joseph, 2023). This has necessitated the to explore other ways of salvaging the situation. Thus, this study sought to find out if the use of 7Es learning cycle and Problem-Based learning strategy will enhance students' performance in wave motion.

Statement of the Research Problem

Evidences abound of underperformance in Physics especially in wave motion among male and female students in senior secondary schools with most students unable to obtain a credit pass (WAEC, Chief Examiners' Report, 2015 -2022). The dwindling performance of male and female students in Physics particularly in wave motion continue to attract considerable attention from government, researchers, curriculum planners, concerned teachers, parents and students.

The fear is that performing poorly in Physics concepts like wave motion may affect male and female students desire to acquire high education in Physics and Physics related areas, thereby, limiting manpower production, scientific and technological development of the nation. Research evidences indicate that the major reasons for persistent low performance in Physics are students' perception of the subject as being abstract. Others are teachers use of defective instructional strategies which produces students with poor problem solving ability, inability to reason critically and lack of curiosity about science especially Physics concepts like wave motion.

It is therefore imperative that innovative instructional strategies of improving students' performance be applied. Consequently, this study aimed to find out the efficacy of 7Es and problem-based learning strategies. The problem of the study posed in questions form is: Will the use of 7Es learning cycle and Problem-Based learning strategy enhance students' performance in wave motion?

Objectives of the Study: The study sought to:

1. determined the mean academic performance scores of secondary school students taught wave motion using 7Es learning model and those exposed to Problem-Based Learning Strategy in Bauchi Metropolis.
2. determined the mean difference in the academic performance scores of male and female students taught wave motion using the 7E learning model in Bauchi Metropolis.
3. determined the mean difference in the academic performance scores of male and female students taught wave motion using Problem-Based Learning Strategy in Bauchi Metropolis.

Research Questions: The following research questions were asked to guide the study.

1. What is the mean academic performance scores of secondary school students taught wave motion using 7Es learning model and those exposed to Problem-Based Learning Strategy in Bauchi Metropolis?
2. What is the mean difference in the academic performance scores of male and female students taught wave motion using the 7E learning model in Bauchi Metropolis?
3. What is the mean difference in the academic performance scores of male and female students taught wave motion using Problem-Based Learning Strategy in Bauchi Metropolis?

Effects of 7Es Model ... (Omega & Kpianyam, 2024) DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11432175>

Hypotheses: The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant difference between the mean academic performance scores of students taught wave motion using the 7Es Learning Model and those taught using Problem-Based Learning Strategy in Bauchi Metropolis.
2. There is no significant difference between the mean academic performance scores of male and female students taught wave motion using the 7Es learning model in Bauchi Metropolis.
3. There is no significant difference between the mean academic performance scores of male and female students taught wave motion using Problem-Based learning strategy in Bauchi Metropolis.

Methodology

The study employed pre-test post-test, non-randomized quasi-experimental research design involving two treatment groups. The design was considered appropriate for the study because it is more reliable to use natural intact classes than forming a group through randomization of subjects which makes the subjects suspicious of an unusual activity taking place which may influence the outcome of the study. The subjects used for the study were assigned to two experimental groups. One group was taught wave motion using the 7Es learning model while the second group was taught wave motion using Problem-Based learning strategy. Population consisted of 3,579 Senior Secondary Two (SS II) students in 22 public secondary schools located within Bauchi Town offering Physics in the 2022/2023 academic session (Bauchi State Ministry of Education, 2023). Sample comprised 128 students consisting of 71 male and 57 female SS II students offering physics which was obtained using simple random sampling technique through balloting. Of the two schools sampled, wave motion was taught in one using the 7Es learning model and in the second using Problem-Based Learning Strategy.

The instrument used for data collection was Wave Motion Performance Test (WMPT), the WMPT comprised 20 multiple choice questions with options A-D. The questions were adopted from past WAEC and NECO examination questions. This was done to ensure that the questions used for the study were valid and reliable. Reliability coefficient of 0.80 was obtained using Kuder-Richardson Formula-21 (K-R₂₁) to determine the internal consistency of the instrument.

Before commencement of treatment, the students were pre-tested. After administering the pre-test, students were exposed to treatment using 7Es learning model and Problem-Based Learning Strategy. The treatment lasted for three weeks after which a post-test was administered to them. In answering the research questions, mean and standard deviation was used while Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the formulated null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

The results of data analysis and interpretation are presented according to the research questions asked and hypotheses formulated for the study.

Research Question 1

What is the mean academic performance scores of secondary school students taught wave motion using 7Es learning model and those exposed to Problem-Based Learning Strategy in Bauchi Metropolis?

Table 1: Pre-WMPT and Post-WMPT Mean and Standard Deviation of 7Es Learning Model and Problem-Based Learning Strategy

Instructional Strategy		Pre-WMPT	Post-WMPT	Mean gain
7E Learning	N	62	62	
	Mean	22.37	30.27	7.90
	Std. Dev	4.42	7.07	
Problem Based Learning	N	66	66	
	Mean	20.97	31.27	10.30
	Std. Dev	5.82	6.13	
	Mean diff.			2.40

Result in Table 1 shows that students taught wave motion using 7Es model had a mean score of 22.37 in pre-WMPT with standard deviation of 4.42 and mean score of 30.27 and standard deviation of 7.07 in the post-WMPT. Students taught wave motion using PBL strategy had a mean score of 20.97 and standard deviation of 5.82 in the pre-WMPT and mean score of 31.27 with a standard deviation of 6.13 in the post-WMPT. The result in the table further shows that mean gain in

Effects of 7Es Model ... (Omaga & Kpianyam, 2024) DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11432175>

performance of students taught wave motion using 7Es model is 7.90 while that of PBL is 10.30. The difference in the mean scores of students taught wave motion using 7Es model those taught wave motion using PBL is 2.40.

Research Question 2

What is the mean difference in the academic performance scores of male and female students taught wave motion using the 7E learning model in Bauchi Metropolis?

Table 2: Pre-WMPT and Post-WMPT mean and Standard Deviation showing Male and Female Students taught Wave Motion using 7Es learning model.

Students' Gender		Pre-WMPT	Post-WMPT	Mean gain
Male	N	35	35	
	Mean	22.86	31.20	8.34
	Std. Dev.	4.03	8.26	
Female	N	27	27	
	Mean	21.74	29.07	7.33
	Std. Dev.	4.90	5.00	
Mean diff.				1.01

Result in Table 2 shows that the mean scores for male students taught wave motion using the 7Es learning model is 22.86 with standard deviation of 4.03 in the pre-WMPT and a mean score of 31.20 with standard deviation of 8.26 in the post-WMPT. Female students taught wave motion using 7Es learning model had a mean score of 21.74 with standard deviation of 4.90 in the pre-WMPT and mean score of 29.07 with standard deviation of 5.00 in the post-WMPT. The mean gain in performance of male students is 8.34 while for female students, it is 7.33. The mean difference in performance of male and female students taught wave motion using 7Es learning model is 1.01.

Research Question 3

What is the mean difference in the academic performance scores of male and female students taught wave motion using Problem-Based Learning Strategy in Bauchi Metropolis?

Table 3: Pre-WMPT and Post-WMPT mean and Standard Deviation Scores of Male and Female Students taught Wave Motion using PBL Strategy

Students' Gender		Pre-WMPT	Post-WMPT	Mean gain
Male	N	36	36	
	Mean	20.97	32.97	12.00
	Std. Deviation	5.42	4.99	
Female	N	30	30	
	Mean	20.97	29.23	8.26
	Std. Deviation	6.35	6.80	
Mean Diff.				3.74

Result in Table 3 shows that the mean scores for male students taught wave motion using PBL strategy is 20.97 with standard deviation of 5.42 in the pre-WMPT and mean score of 32.97 with standard deviation of 4.99 in the post-WMPT. Female students taught wave motion using PBL strategy had mean score of 20.97 with standard deviation of 6.35 in the pre-WMPT and a mean score of 29.23 and standard deviation of 6.80 in the post-WMPT. The mean gain in performance of male students is 12.00 while for female students, it is 8.26. The mean difference in performance of male and female students taught wave motion using PBL strategy is 3.74.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between the mean academic performance scores of students taught wave motion using the 7Es Learning Model and those taught using Problem-Based Learning Strategy in Bauchi Metropolis.

Table 4: ANCOVA Result of Students taught Wave Motion using 7Es Learning Model and PBL Strategy

Effects of 7Es Model ... (Omaga & Kpianyam, 2024) DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11432175>

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	472.433 ^a	2	236.216	5.848	.004
Intercept	3611.347	1	3611.347	89.410	.000
Pre-Test	440.558	1	440.558	10.907	.001
Strategy	70.927	1	70.927	1.756	.188
Error	5048.872	125	40.391		
Total	126861.000	128			
Corrected Total	5521.305	127			

R Squared = .086 (Adjusted R Squared = .071)

Result in Table 4 reveals that $F(1, 125) = 1.756$ at $P = 0.188 > 0.05$. Since the p-value of 0.188 is greater than the alpha value of 0.05, the null hypothesis is retained. By implication, there is no significant difference between the mean academic performance scores of students taught wave motion using the 7Es Learning Model and those taught using Problem-Based Learning Strategy in Bauchi Metropolis.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference between the mean academic performance scores of male and female students taught wave motion using the 7Es learning model in Bauchi Metropolis.

Table 5: ANCOVA Results of Male and Female Students taught Wave Motion using 7Es Learning Model

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	387.518 ^a	2	193.759	4.303	.018
Intercept	783.284	1	783.284	17.394	.000
Pre-Test	318.631	1	318.631	7.076	.010
Gender	35.813	1	35.813	.795	.376
Error	2656.821	59	45.031		
Total	59869.000	62			
Corrected Total	3044.339	61			

R Squared = .127 (Adjusted R Squared = .098)

Result in Table 5 reveals that $F(1, 59) = 0.795$ at $P = 0.376 > 0.05$. Since the p-value of 0.376 is greater than the alpha value of 0.05, the null hypothesis is retained. By implication, there is no significant difference between the mean academic performance scores of male and female students taught wave motion using the 7Es learning model in Bauchi Metropolis.

Hypothesis 3

There is no significant difference between the mean academic performance scores of male and female students taught wave motion using Problem-Based learning strategy in Bauchi Metropolis.

Table 6: ANCOVA Results of Male and Female Students taught Wave Motion using PBL Strategy

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	378.625 ^a	2	189.313	5.772	.005
Intercept	3053.026	1	3053.026	93.077	.000
Pre-Test	149.873	1	149.873	4.569	.036
Gender	228.575	1	228.575	6.969	.010
Error	2066.466	63	32.801		
Total	66992.000	66			
Corrected Total	2445.091	65			

Effects of 7Es Model ... (Omega & Kpianyam, 2024) DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11432175>

R Squared = .155 (Adjusted R Squared = .128)

Result in table 6 shows that $F(1, 63) = 6.969$ at $P = 0.010 < 0.05$. Since the p-value of 0.010 is less than the alpha value of 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected. By implication, there is significant difference between the mean academic performance scores of male and female students taught wave motion using Problem-Based learning strategy in Bauchi Metropolis.

Discussion of Findings

Results from hypothesis one shows that no significant difference between the mean academic performance scores of students taught wave motion using the 7Es Learning Model and those taught using Problem-Based Learning Strategy in Bauchi Metropolis. The outcome in this study however, does not confirm with that of Cheron, Samikwo and Kabesa (2021) whose result showed statistical significant difference between the mean scores of students taught using 7Es learning cycle and those taught using the conventional instructional method. However, Cheron, Samikwo and Kabesa (2021) compared 7Es learning cycle with a conventional instructional method and used t-test without determining group homogeneity. These reasons may account for the inconsistency in findings. The finding in this study means that adopting effective instructional strategies like 7Es learning cycle and PBL will enhance meaningful learning and improve performance in Physics concepts like wave motion.

The finding of hypothesis two reveals that there is no significant difference between the mean academic performance scores of male and female students taught wave motion using the 7Es learning model in Bauchi Metropolis. This means that the use of 7Es learning model can enhance students' academic performance irrespective of gender. This is in agreement with research findings by Ibrahim, Lakpini, Abdulkarim and Falau (2022) and Shalini and Anurag, (2018) who said that 7Es learning model can improve students' academic performance irrespective of their gender. This implies that 7Es learning model is gender friendly.

Finding from hypothesis three reveals that a significant difference between the mean academic performance scores of male and female students taught wave motion using Problem-Based learning strategy in Bauchi Metropolis. This implies that male students performed better than their female counterparts when taught wave motion using PBL strategy. This contradicts research findings by Omega (2017), Ajai and Imoko (2015), Anyafulude (2014) who found that PBL strategy is non-discriminatory as regards gender, that is, it enhances the academic performance of both male and female students.

Conclusion

The use of innovative learning strategies such as 7Es learning cycle and Problem-Based learning strategy helped enhanced students' academic performance particularly in wave motion. However, as regards gender, the use of 7Es was found to enhance students' academic performance irrespective of gender but with PBL male students performed better than their female counterparts in wave motion.

Recommendations

It is therefore recommended that:

1. Physics teachers should endeavour to use innovative learning strategies such as the 7Es learning model to improve students' performance in wave motion.
2. Workshops, seminars and conferences could be organized to enlighten Physics teachers on the use of innovative strategies such as 7Es model to help improve male and female students' academic performance in Physics.
3. The PBL strategy should be used with care in attempt to improve male and female students' performance in wave motion.

Acknowledgements

The authors wish to express profound gratitude to eminent researchers whose works contributed immensely to this study. Also appreciated are the Principals, Physics teachers (research assistants) and Senior Secondary II students for the cooperation, physical assistance, patience and understanding they showed during this research work.

References

- Abuh, Y. P. (2021). Gender and assessment of physics students' academic performance in senior secondary school SSIII Olamaboro local government area of Kogi state, Nigeria, *African Journal of Science, Technology and Mathematics Education*. 6(2) 1-9.

Effects of 7Es Model ... (Omega & Kpianyam, 2024) DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11432175>

- Achor, E.E. (2020). *Cognitive dimensions in demystifying abstract concepts in Physics*. Inaugural lecture series held at Benue State University, Makurdi on the 20th February, 2020.
- Adesoji, F. A., & Idika, M. I. (2015). Effects of 7Es learning cycle model and case-based learning strategy on secondary school students learning outcomes in chemistry. *Journal of the International Society for Teacher Education*, 19(1), 7-17.
- Adeyemo, S.A., Babajide, V.F.T., & Iwuji, O.C. (2014). Combating the menace of students' difficulties in physics for developmental goals in Nigeria. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Development, Education and Science Research*, 2(1)178-189.
- Ajai, J. T., & Imoko, B.I. (2015). Gender differences in mathematics achievement and retention scores: A case of problem-based learning method. *International Journal of Research in Education and Science*, 1(1) 45-50.
- Al-Eid, W. (2014). The effect of teaching a suggested unit based on 7E model in the development of mathematical communication skills in geometry and their retention by the 9th grade students in Shiraz city. *The Turkish Online Journal of Design, Arts and Communication*, 2, 341-346.
- Anyafulude, J. (2014). Effect of Problem-based learning strategy on students' achievement in senior secondary schools chemistry in Enugu State. *Journal of Research and Method in Education*, 4(3), 27-31.
- Assem, H.D., Nartey, L., Appiah, E., & Aidoo, J.K. (2023). A review of students' academic performance in physics: attitude, instructional methods, misconceptions and teachers qualification. *European Journal of Education and Pedagogy*, 4(1), 84-92.
- Balta, N., & Sarac, H. (2016). The effect of 7E learning cycle on learning science teaching: A meta-analysis study. *European Journal of Educational Research*, 5(2), 61-72.
- Bauchi State Ministry of Education, (2023). Record and statistics department.
- Bunkure, Y.I. (2019). Efficacy of 5E learning strategy in enhancing academic achievement in physics among students in Rano Education Zone, Kano State, Nigeria. *Journal of Science Technology and Education*, 1(3), 296-304.
- Bybee, R.W. (1997). *Achieving scientific literacy: From purpose to practice*. Portsmouth, N.H: Heinemann Publication.
- Cakir, N. K. (2017). Effect of 5E learning model on academic achievement, attitude and science process skills. Meta-analysis study. *Journal of Education and Training Studies*, 5(11), 157
- Cherono, J., Samikwo, D., & Kabesa S. (2020). Effect of 7E learning cycle model on students' academic achievement in biology in secondary schools in Chesumei Subcounty, Kenya. *African Journal of Education, Science and Technology*, 6(3), 312-322.
- Filtri, S. (2019). Improving and learning algebra in upper basic schools using inquiry approach. *International Journal of Research in Education and Science*, 2(3), 15-25.
- Haruna, A.S. (2019). Preference for Teacher's Gender among undergraduate students of Science Education in Federal College of Education, Kano. *Kano Journal of Educational Psychology* 1 (1), 102 – 111.
- Ibrahim, A., Lakpini, M. A., Abdulkarim, B., & Falau, M. K. (2022). Effect of 7E learning cycle on cell concept performance among secondary school slow learners in Kastina Metropolis, Nigeria. *Kashere Journal of Education*, 3(1), 138-145.
- Josiah, M. M., & Mankilik, M. (2021). Jigsaw IV cooperative learning strategy. Closing the gender and school type gaps in physics achievement of senior secondary two students. *British Journal of Developmental Psychology*, 4(2), 18-30.
- Khataibeh, A. (2005). *Teaching science for all*. Jordan: Al-Maseerah Publishing Company.
- Kpiranyam, F.S., Agbideye, A., & Ukor, D.D. (2022). Comparative effects of student team achievement division and assertive questioning instructional strategies on Nigerian students' critical thinking and performance in biology. *Journal of the International Centre for Science, Humanities and Education Research*, 5(2), 98-108.
- Mergendoller, J.R., Maxwell, N.L., & Bellisimo, Y. (2002). The effectiveness of problem-based instruction: A comparative study of instructional methods and students' characteristics. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Problem-Based Learning*, 1(2) 49-69.
- Nnamani S. C., & Oyibe O. A. (2016). Gender and academic achievement of secondary school students in social studies in Abakaliki Urban of Ebonyi state. *British Journal of Education*. 4(8), 72-83.
- Offordile, E. O., Umeano, E. C., Adene, F. M., Obi, S. C., Ugwuanyi, C. S., Okeke, C. I., & Adimora, D. E. (2021). Improving the academic achievement of low achieving secondary school students in physics using peer tutoring learning strategy. *International Journal of Mechanical and Production Engineering Research and Development*, 11(3) 201–212.
- Ogonna, C.S. & Joseph, B.I. (2023). Gender difference in cooperative learning in secondary school students' academic achievement in physics. *International Journal of advanced Multidisciplinary Research and Studies*, 3(3), 912-919.

Effects of 7Es Model ... (Omaga & Kpianyam, 2024) DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11432175>

- Omaga, J.O. (2017). *Effect of problem-based learning approach on secondary students' interest and achievement in physics in Bauchi State, Nigeria*. Unpublished PhD Thesis, Federal University of Agriculture, Makurdi, Benue State.
- Omebe, C. A., & Akani O. (2015). Effect of instructional resources on student's achievement in physics and chemistry in secondary schools in Ebonyi state, Nigeria, *European journal of training and development studies*, 2(2), 56-65.
- Onyilo, F.A., Agernor, T., Kpiranyam, F.S., & Wirba, C. (2022). Comparative effects of scaffolding and 5Es instructional strategies on students' academic performance in Physics in Benue State, Nigeria. *BSU Journal of Science, Mathematics and Computer education*, 3(1), 122-131.
- Sadeq, M. (2003). Effectiveness of using the 7Es constructivist model in teaching science on the development of achievement and other science processes skills among the 2nd preparatory class students. *Scientific Education Journal*, 6(3), 145-190.
- Shalini, S., & Anurag, S. (2018). 7E learning cycle: A paradigm shift in instructional approach. *Shanlax International Journal of Education*, 6(2), 13-22.
- Strobel Education (2023). Unlocking the benefits of innovative teaching strategies. retrieved from <https://strobeleducation.com>blog>
- The Hun School of Princeton (2020). What is problem-based learning? <https://www.hunschool.org>proble>
- Ukwuru, J.O., Eriba, J.O., Ogbeba, J. (2022). Effects of 4As and 5Es instructional models on senior secondary II students' academic performance in chemical equilibrium in Benue. *BSU Journal of Science, Mathematics and Computer education*, 3(1), 83-97.
- Usman, I.S., & Yakubu, H. (2020). Effect of physics practical on students' attitude and performance in Bauchi Educational Zone. *Journal of Science, Technology and Education*, 8(2), 260-271.
- WAEC Chief Examiners Report (2015-2021). Students' performance in physics. Retrieved on 10th February, 2024 from <https://www.waeconline.org.ng/elearning/Physics/physmain.html>